

Geospatial Network of Internees in Switzerland during the Second World War – A Proof of Concept

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Advancing digitisation is heralding a transformative shift in the role of archives. Beyond the task of preserving physical documents, archives increasingly deal with born-digital documents or digital representations of the documents, presenting new opportunities to enhance the accessibility of their collections. Furthermore, there is the prospect of reimagining accessibility and tailoring methods to specific digitised collections. (Sahle 2007) As Kramer (2014) puts it, the boundary between a digital archive and the product of historical research and interpretation becomes permeable.

This paper explores historical network research as a potential tool for digital archiving from three vantage points. First, the method includes the extraction and enrichment of data from digital artifacts by linking or georeferencing and thus contributes to the metadata available for a collection through or in addition to the archival database. Second, resulting visualisations can serve as a user interface, which is more intuitive than the hierarchical archive catalogue and allows for additional metadata filters. Lastly, subsequent network metrics can offer historical insight, inspiring new avenues of research into collections.

It does so by presenting a proof of concept that is being developed by the Swiss Federal Archives (SFA) for a collection of index cards by the Eidgenössische Kommissariat für Internierung und Hospitalisierung (EKIH), each identifying one internee in Switzerland during the Second World War and containing more than 100'000 cards. These cards are phonetically ordered by surname in the archive's repository but also contain information on each soldier's place of origin and a list of each internment location. The recent digitisation of the letters K and L has paved the way for enhancing archival description through the creation of a pipeline that combines Google Vision API and Chatgpt4 for data extraction and classification. This

enhanced archival description improves accessibility for researchers seeking specific individuals. However, the resulting dataset also holds a historical macro perspective, which can be actualised by enriching the obtained data through georeferencing, visualising it as a GIS network of camps through which internees were transported and analysing calculated network metrics.

The dataset detailing the exact geospatial movements of people subjected to state-planned forced migration occurring both across and within Swiss borders is a compelling source for historical network analysis which had traditionally focused on international and voluntary migration as well as aggregated geospatial data. (Pitoski, Lampoltshammer und Parycek 2021, 2-3) Visualising these movements as a network might provide insight into how the Swiss state treated groups of internees of different nationalities and the opportunities for contact separate groups might have had with each other during their internment.

This paper discusses the main challenges that were posed by georeferencing historical placenames and placenames that have been misinterpreted by handwritten text recognition through the assistance of gazetteers and specialised machine learning algorithms and considers the benefit of using large language models for quantitative data extraction over more traditional methods such as layout analysis. The discussion also addresses the importance of presenting uncertainties in visualisations and how to make them explicit and comprehensible to users. (Dunn 2012)

References

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